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Isolation and Identification of Microorganisms from Soil Enriched With Different Fertilizers in Field Cultivation with Rice

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Abstract

Microorganisms are able to convert fertilizers that contain nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium and minerals in the soil for their growth. Seven samples (Control, PU, GU+P&K, PU+P&K, GU+P&K+FYM, PU+P&K+FYM) of the post-planting soil of rice used for isolation and identification of bacteria and fungi. A total of five bacterial species were isolated from the experimental plots which include *Diplobacillus* species, *Streptococcus* species, *Streptobacillus* species, *Coccobacillus* species and *Staphylococcus* species. Bacteria isolated were mainly rod and cocci in shape. *Diplobacillus* spp and *Streptobacillus* spp have single arrangement and is Gram negative. *Streptococcus* spp and *Coccobacillus* spp have chain arrangement and is Gram positive. *Staphylococcus* spp are cluster in arrangement and is Gram positive. Total viable colony counts of the bacterial isolates ranged from $1.04 \times 10^3 - 9.60 \times 10^3$ and $1.40 \times 10^5 - 8.00 \times 10^5$. A total of thirteen genera of fungi were isolated from plots treated with different fertilizers. The majority of isolates were members of the genus *Phoma*. The combination of inorganic and organic fertilizers significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased fungal counts over control (8.0×10^5) The control (zero application) had lower isolates due to no (fertilizer application) to the soil. The combination of inorganic and organic fertilizers significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased fungal counts over control (8.0×10^5).

Keywords: Bacteria, biofertilizer, Fungi, inorganic fertilizer, Isolation

INTRODUCTION

Soil nutrients availability and decomposition of organic matter depends on microorganism. Microbe creates foods like nitrogen, carbon, oxygen, hydrogen, phosphorus, potassium and trace minerals for the plants. It is the microbes that convert the NPK and minerals in the soil into a form plants can use them for growth and production (Parr *et al.*, 1994). These microbes include algae, protozoa, bacteria and fungi. Many microbes need organic carbon to live; they get this from wood chips, leaves, manures and other organic matter, they creates humus which increases soil structure, root penetration and development. Soil microorganisms (flora and fauna), depend entirely on soil for their nutrition, growth and activity. The major soil factor which influences the microbial populations, distributions in soil are: soil fertility, cultural practices, soil moisture, soils temperature and soil aeration. Others include light soil pH, organic matter, food and energy supply, nature of soil and microbial association. All these factors play a great role in determining not only the number and type of organisms but also their activities (Schilz and Jorgensen, 2001).

Microbes improve soil structure by the humus they create while digesting organic matter and help in nitrogen fixation (Max, 2012). Application of manure to soil affects microbial communities. Manure additions to soil have beneficial effects on nutrient cycling, soil microbial biomass, soil microbial activity and enzymatic processes (Czurak-Dainard, 2005).

Bacteria are microscopic organisms. When viewed under the microscope, they have three distinct shapes Bacilli-rod-shaped, Cocci-sphere-shaped and Spirilli-spiral-shaped. Bacteria can be identified and classified by their shape (Parr *et al.*, 1994).

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Fungi are diverse microorganisms that inhabit different environments such as soil, plant parts (leaves, root and fruits), water and food (Maheswari and Komalavalli, 2013; Sartori *et al.*, 2013; Rebecca *et al.*, 2012). The growth and distribution of fungi are affected by different environmental factors such as temperature, pH, moisture, and degree of aeration, as well as amount and type of nutrients (Gaddeyya *et al.*, 2012). Soil fungi play an important and vital role in maintaining soil fertility and productivity, and are influenced by a number of factors, including soil properties and human activities (Bao *et al.*, 2012). They play an important part in nutrition and processes that lead to the improvement of the health and development of plants (Mulani and Turukmane, 2014).

The aims and objectives of this work are to isolate and identify the bacteria and fungi associated with soil enriched with different fertilizers after the cultivation of rice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

EXPERIMENTAL SITE

The Laboratory analysis was carried out at the Agronomy Laboratory, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

SAMPLES USED FOR ISOLATION

Seven samples of the post-planting soil of rice based on the treatments (Control, PU, GU+P&K, PU+P&K, GU+P&K+FYM, PU+P&K+FYM) were taken to laboratory for isolation and identification of bacteria and fungi.

ISOLATION OF BACTERIA

One gram from each of the soil samples was used in carrying out serial dilution using 9% Sodium chloride as diluents up to 10^6 . Pour plate technique of Robert and Greenwood, (2003) was used. Measured 1ml of 10^3 and 10^5 dilutions were aseptically introduced into sterile petri dishes in duplicate. Sterilized nutrient agar was used for the bacteria isolation. To inhibit yeast and mold growth 50mg/L Nystatin was added aseptically to the cooled sterilized medium just before pouring. Inoculated Petri-dishes were incubated at 37°C for 24-48hours.

IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIA

The bacterial isolates were identified based on their cultural morphological characteristics and biochemical characteristics.

BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION TEST OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES

Biochemical characterization of the bacterial isolates was carried out as described by Ogbulie *et al.*, 1998 vis-a-vis Gram's staining, catalase test, motility test, oxidase test, coagulase test, indole test and sugar fermentation test.

GRAM'S STAINING

A smear of each of the isolates was made on a grease-free slide, air-dried and heat fixed. The smear was covered with crystal violet stain for 1min and wash off with clean distilled water, Gram's iodine was used to flood the smear for 1min and washed off with clean distilled water. The smear was decolourized with acetone for 30secs and washed off with clean distilled water. The counter stain safranin was poured on the smear for 30secs and washed off with clean distilled water and allowed to air dry. Microscopic examination was carried out using at X100 objective after applying oil immersion.

CATALASE TEST

Two drops of hydrogen peroxide was placed on a grease-free slide. A clean glass rod was used to transfer a discrete colony of an isolate onto the hydrogen peroxide and observed for effervescence.

MOTILITY TEST

The motility medium was sterilized at 121°C for 15min by autoclaving. Freshly prepared bacterial isolates were inoculated into cooled sterilized motility medium at the centre and incubated at 37°C for 24hours.

OXIDASE TEST

Freshly prepared oxidase reagent was sterilized and allowed to cool. Filter papers were placed on clean petri dishes. Two drops of cooled sterilized oxidase reagent were added to the filter papers and stirred with sterile wooden sticks. Freshly prepared bacterial isolates were smeared on the filter papers containing the sterilized oxidase reagents and observed for 10seconds for colour change (blue-purple colour indicate positive reaction).

COAGULASE TEST

Coagulase test was carried out by slide method. A drop of physiological saline was placed on grease-free slides. Freshly prepared bacterial isolates were emulsified into the saline to make two thick suspensions. A drop of plasma was added to one of the suspension and mixed properly for 10 seconds. The second suspension served as control. Clumping of the bacterial isolate indicate coagulase positive.

INDOLE TEST

Freshly prepared bacterial isolates were inoculated into 1% sterilized peptone water and incubated for 48hours at 37°C. Kovac's reagent (0.5ml) was added after incubation and shaken gently. Appearance of red colour indicate indole positive.

SUGAR FERMENTATION TEST

This was carried out to determine the ability of the bacterial isolate to ferment the following sugars: glucose, maltose, and lactose. The basal medium used was Hugh and Leifson's medium. Measured 9ml of the basal medium was dispensed into test tubes containing inverted Durham's tubes in duplicates. The sugars were made up to 2% of the basal medium. The test tubes were plugged with cotton wool and sterilized at 121°C for 10min. After cooling each test tube was inoculated with freshly prepared bacterial isolate and incubated at 37°C for 24hour. The test tubes were observed for colour change.

ISOLATION OF FUNGI

One gram from each of the soil samples was used in carrying out serial dilution using 9% Sodium chloride as diluents up to 10⁶. Pour plate technique of Robert and Greenwood, (2003) was used. Measured 1ml of 10³ and 10⁵ dilutions were aseptically introduced into sterile petri dishes in duplicates. Sterilized Potato dextrose agar (PDA) was used for the fungi isolation. Chloramphenicol (250mg/L) was added to the cooled sterilized Potato dextrose agar to inhibit bacterial growth. Inoculated Petri-dishes were left at room temperature for 4 day to allow the growth of fungi.

IDENTIFICATION OF FUNGI

The fungal isolates were identified based on their cultural and morphological characteristics. The microscopic examination of the isolates was carried out using wet staining with lactophenol cotton blue and observation was carried out using X40 objective (Gaddeyya *et al.*, 2012).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

SAS (2005) was used to analyze the data obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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A total of five species of bacterial were isolated from the experimental plots which include *Diplobacillus* species, *Streptococcus* species, *Streptobacillus* species, *Coccobacillus* species and *Staphylococcus* species. Bacteria isolated were mainly rod and cocci in shape. *Diplobacillus* spp and *Streptobacillus* spp have single arrangement and is Gram negative. *Streptococcus* spp and *Coccobacillus* spp have chain arrangement and is Gram positive. *Staphylococcus* spp are cluster in arrangement and is Gram positive. Total viable colony counts of the bacterial isolates ranged from $1.04 \times 10^3 - 9.60 \times 10^3$ and $1.40 \times 10^5 - 8.00 \times 10^5$ (Table 1).

Diplobacillus spp. was catalase, oxidase, coagulase, indole and maltose negative but glucose and lactose positive. *Streptococcus* spp was catalase, oxidase, coagulase, indole and maltose negative but glucose positive. *Streptobacillus* spp was catalase, indole and lactose negative and oxidase, coagulase, glucose and maltose positive. *Coccobacillus* spp was catalase, oxidase, coagulase, lactose and maltose negative but indole and glucose positive. *Staphylococcus* spp was catalase and lactose positive but oxidase, coagulase, indole, glucose and maltose negative (Table 2). Morphologically, the colonies were discrete, circular, raised and restricted. The highest count of bacterial were found in plots where GU+P&K+FYM and PU+P&K+FYM were applied, however, GU+P&K+FYM had the highest count of (1.8×10^5 cfu/g) (Table 3). The least bacterial counts were in control plots with values (1.2×10^4 cfu/g). The increased in the total count of bacteria can be explained in two ways; the microorganisms present in the organic fertilizer might be due to the source of carbon for bacteria colonizing the soil environment. On the other hand, the fertilizing material with macro and microelements promotes the availability of nutrients for the bacteria.

Plots applied with combined fertilizers have the highest number of isolate compared to single fertilizer plots, probably due to their being rich in live microorganisms, when applied to seed, soil or living plants, it increases soil nutrients or makes them biologically available. This finding is in agreement with Olowokere *et al.*, 2013.

Table 1: Total viable count of bacterial and fungal isolates

Treatments	Bacteria 10^3	Bacteria 10^5	Fungi 10^3	Fungi 10^5
Control	1.2×10^4_e	8.00×10^6_a	2.40×10^4_e	3.20×10^5_c
GU	1.04×10^7_f	1.44×10^7_c	4.80×10^4_a	2.00×10^5_e
PU	1.43×10^3_d	1.60×10^5_c	2.80×10^4_d	1.20×10^5_f
GU + P & K	9.60×10^4_a	1.40×10^4_c	4.80×10^4_a	2.40×10^7_d
PU + P & K	1.28×10^5_e	1.60×10^7_c	3.60×10^4_c	6.40×10^5_a
GU + P & K + FYM	1.80×10^5_c	3.60×10^6_b	4.50×10^3_b	3.20×10^6_c
PU + P & K + FYM	9.20×10^4_b	7.60×10^6_a	2.80×10^3_d	4.80×10^5_b
LSD (p < 0.05)	0.10	0.72	0.06	0.06

Values with same letter indicated in columns are not significantly different at 5% level of probability.

TABLE 2: Microscopical and Biochemical Characterization of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial Isolates	<i>Diplobacilli Spp.</i>	<i>Streptococcus Spp.</i>	<i>Streptobacilli Spp.</i>	<i>Coccobacilli Spp.</i>	<i>Staphylococcus Spp.</i>
<u>Microscopical</u>					
Shapes	Rod	Cocci	Rod	Rod	Cocci
Arrangement	Single	Chains	Single	Chains	Cluster
Gram Staining	-	+	-	+	+
Spore Staining	+	-	-	-	-
<u>Biochemical</u>					
Catalase	-	-	-	-	+
Oxidase	-	-	+	-	-
Coagulase	-	-	+	-	-
Indole	-	-	-	+	-
Glucose	+	+	+	+	-
Lactose	+	-	-	-	+
Maltose	-	-	+	-	-

FUNGI

A total of thirteen genera of fungi were isolated from plots treated with different fertilizers. The majority of isolates were members of the genus *Phoma*. The control (zero application) had lower isolates due to no (fertilizer application) to the soil. Makasaki and Ohtaki. (2002) reported that when microorganism is incubated in the presence of two substrates, the variety of microorganism increases. Compost prepared from combination of two or more type of wastes enhanced not only the number of fungi but also the diversity of saprophytic microorganisms that play an important role in the biodegradation of such materials. The combination of inorganic and organic fertilizers significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased fungal counts over control (8.0×10^5) (Table 1). This might be attributed to the fact that organic manure supplied organic carbon for the fungi which are chemo-heterotrophs. This trend can be attributed to the fact that fungi are more acid tolerant (Adebayo, 1997). Fungi exhibits a wide range of important ecological functions especially the ones associated with decomposition of organic substrates in soil. They are also valuable sources of by-products compounds and enzymes that can be of environmental importance (Jaber *et al.*, 2012).

The isolated *Aspergillus* species from compost were *Aspergillus fumigates*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus candidus*. This association of *Aspergillus* species has been reported by Anastasi *et al.* (2005). The isolates corresponded with the work done by Rabia *et al.* (2007). They reported the highest load and number of species of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* in compost. The finding of Storm (1985) was in agreement with these results that the number and diversity of microorganisms are more when two or more waste was used for composting. The abundance of *Penicillium* can be attributed to its universal presence as a saprophyte growing on dead leaves, woods and other decaying vegetation. The spores are widespread and are often associated with organic materials and soil.

Fusarium species were also isolated from the organic base fertilizers. According to Giovano *et al.* (2005) *Fusarium* is another organism associated with organic fertilizers. *Fusarium* species are widely distributed in all soils and are responsible for the decomposition of organic manure by their growth hyphae and are regarded as imperfect fungi. Lesite and Summerell, (2006) identified *Fusarium* species morphologically and

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concluded that the arrangement of their macroconidia on the conidiogenous cells are either singly, false head or chain.

Fungi play important roles as decomposers, plant symbionts and pathogens in soils. The structure of fungal communities in the rhizosphere is the result of complex interactions among selection factors that may favour beneficial or detrimental relationships (Berendsen, (2012).

The application of granular and prilled urea were lower in bacterial count but the control plot had higher count. According to Brzezinska and Wlodarczyk (2005), dehydrogenase activity in the soil is an indicator of the intensity of respiratory metabolism of microorganisms. The analysis of the activity of these enzymes provides information about the content of organic matter or fertility of the substrate.

It is known that if phosphorus content is low, the activity of these enzymes is higher and according to Bielinska and Mocek-Plociniak. (2012), their long-term observations proved that the acid phosphatase enzyme was strictly correlated with the physiochemical properties of soil. Significant low activity of acid phosphatase varies where nitrogen organic fertilizer had been applied. This indicates that microbial combinations provide plants adequate amounts of phosphorus.

microorganisms is not only limited to providing access to mineral compounds. They cause favourable transformations in soil, optimizing the living environment, growth and yield of plants. Positive effects on yield and plant healthiness after application of organic manure were presented in the work of Kowalska. (2016). Apart from that, they participate in transformation of soil organic matter and are decisive to soil structure and its pH. They produce numerous bioactive substances in soil. Soil microorganisms detoxify many chemical compounds which are harmful to other organisms living in this environment, and they eliminate pathogenic organisms (Niewiadomska, 2013).

NPK fertilizer has been associated with increased biomass of fungi in soils of crop systems according to Aira *et al.* (2010). However, whether the dose of fertilizer modifies rhizosphere fungal communities is largely unknown. Increased nitrogen fertilizer dosage has a potential negative impact on carbon cycling in soil and promotes fungal genera with known pathogenic traits, uncovering a negative effect of intensive fertilization.

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Table 3: Fungi isolated from Plots Treated with Different Fertilizers

Treatment	Fungi Isolates					
Control	<i>Aspergillus Spp.</i>	<i>Nigrospora Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>			
G.U. 100%	<i>Alternaria Spp.</i>	<i>Collectorichum Spp.</i>	<i>Fusarium Spp.</i>	<i>Nigrospora Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>	<i>Rhizopus Spp.</i>
P.U. 100%	<i>Alternaria Spp.</i>	<i>Collectorichum Spp.</i>	<i>Fusarium Spp.</i>	<i>Nigrospora Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>	<i>Rhizopus Spp.</i>
G.U. + P&K	<i>Aspergillus Spp.</i>	<i>Bipolaris Spp.</i>	<i>Chaetomium Spp.</i>	<i>Oidium Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia Spp.</i>
P.U. + P&K	<i>Aspergillus Spp.</i>	<i>Bipolaris Spp.</i>	<i>Chaetomium Spp.</i>	<i>Oidium Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia Spp.</i>
G.U. + P&K + FYM	<i>Nigrospora Spp.</i>	<i>Oidium Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>	<i>Rhizoctoria Spp.</i>	<i>Septoria Spp.</i>	
P.U +P&K + FYM	<i>Nigrospora Spp.</i>	<i>Oidium Spp.</i>	<i>Phoma Spp.</i>	<i>Rhizoctoria Spp.</i>	<i>Septoria Spp.</i>	

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Fig. 2: Fungi Isolates

PLATE 1: Bacteria Isolates as viewed under microscope

PLATE 2 Fungi isolates as viewed under microscope

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